

MORPHOMETRY AND PARASITE DIVERSITY IN *SPILOPELIA SENEGALENSIS* (LINNAEUS, 1766) CAPTURED WITHIN UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN

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ABSTRACT

Laughing doves are widely known for their adaptability to urban and semi-urban environments. Assessing parasite load in birds especially laughing dove is crucial for monitoring their overall as well as ecological health. The goal of this study was to determine morphometric parameters and diversity of parasites species in laughing doves, *Spilopella senegalensis* (Linnaeus, 1766) captured within University of Ibadan. Selected morphometric parameters were determined while ectoparasites and endoparasites [in blood, gastrointestinal tract (GIT)] and faeces respectively, were collected, using standard methods. Statistical significant difference between the morphometric parameters of male and female was noted in body length ($p=0.037$) and live weight ($p=0.013$). Most prevalent ectoparasite and haemoparasite observed in the sampled birds were *Megninia* sp. (60%) and *Haemoproteus* sp. (65%), respectively while *Eimeria* oocysts were observed to be most prevalent in the intestinal contents (90%) and faecal samples (25%). There is need for better wildlife health assessments to mollify risks associated with parasitic infections.

Key words: Avian morphometry, ectoparasites, gastrointestinal helminths, protozoa, *Spilopelia senegalensis*.

Introduction

Birds are warm-blooded vertebrates of diverse groups, distinguished by unique features such as feathers, beaks, possessing specific as well as varied foraging strategies and inhabiting a wide-ranging array of ecologically distinct habitats. The evolution of flight has been pivotal in allowing these species to occupy different habitats or niches (Terrill et Shultz 2023) which has been instrumental in their adaptation and survival with an impressive ecological diversity. They are vital indicators of ecosystem health (Sekercioglu *et al.* 2016) whose abundance and distribution of bird species are influenced by the spatio-temporal availability of key environmental resources and conditions. Among the avian species are laughing doves which are typically found in human-modified environments (Madkour *et al.* 2018) and whose dietary specialization is majorly granivorous. They are also known as Palm Doves (Jennings 2010) with characteristic black-spotted reddish fore-neck as well as a dark-grey rump that distinguishable them from other doves (Serle *et al.* 1977) and their adults having a distinctive patch of rufous and grey on the sides of the neck, composed of split feathers (Abd Rabou et Abd Rabou 2019). Their interaction and acclimatization to the presence of humans avail them food, water and protection against predators (Møller et Díaz 2018).

Avian morphometry encompasses a wide range of parameters used to study birds' physical characteristics, physiological adaptations, and ecological functions. These measurements provide

crucial insights into geographical variation within species, growth and classification of birds (Töpfer 2018) as well as sexual variations (Pohlen *et al.* 2021). Disparity in morphometric characteristics among avian populations may be related to bird age, sex and species. On-site measurements of morphometric parameters are less invasive and economical (Nepshinsky *et al.* 2021) whilst contributing towards understanding species' ecological roles and survival geared towards enhancing effective strategies. Morphometric traits can be influenced by environmental factors such as chemical stressors as well as parasites which are thought to have significant impacts on avian health (Hamza et Ndams 2024).

Parasites are host-dependent organisms that are characteristic of greatly benefiting (nutrients, shelter and other resources) from the host while simultaneously causing harm and yielding no immediate benefits for their hosts (Ali *et al.* 2021). Ectoparasites live on host's external body parts (Weber *et al.* 2018) while endoparasites are located in the internal parts (typically within the blood stream, digestive tract or other internal organs) of the host's body (Pulatov *et al.* 2023). Overwhelming avian parasitic infections can be of serious concern and with severe health implications like growth retardation, intestinal obstruction, morphological alterations severe anaemia, and even mortality (Ayadi *et al.* 2018). As laughing doves frequently inhabit urban and peri-urban environments, they have close interactions with human populations, which increases the risks of exposure to parasites and pathogens that may have zoonotic potentials (Fahmy 2019). Identifying parasite types and load as well as the severity of infestation is crucial in understanding the multitude of effects being exerted on avian hosts especially as it influences their health, behaviour and overall fitness. Data on morphometric parameter and parasite prevalence in laughing dove within University of Ibadan are sparse. Hence, this study examined the morphometric parameters and parasite prevalence in Laughing Dove (*Spilopelia senegalensis*) captured within University of Ibadan main campus.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The University of Ibadan in Ibadan-North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria (7.37760°N, 3.94710°E) was the study area. The university campus which is recognized for its lush green campus, was established in 1948 and provides a conducive habitat for a wide variety of bird species. The campus' diverse vegetation makes it an ideal location for laughing doves and many other bird species, contributing to the University's rich biodiversity (Aderounmu *et al.* 2017). The experimental setup was located in the Aviary Unit in Department of Wildlife and Ecotourism Management's Domestication Centre. The Aviary Unit, equipped for the controlled care of bird species, provides an ideal environment for research on avian species.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was sought from the Animal Care and Use Research Ethics Committee (ACUREC) in the University of Ibadan before the study commenced. The research complied with all relevant national regulations as well as institutional guidelines and was given unconditional approval by the ethics committee with reference UI-ACUREC/141-0924/11.

Experimental Animals and Design

A sample of 20 laughing doves comprising of 16 males and 4 females were captured (opportunistic sampling) using a 12 m by 2.5 m mist net set at ten (10) different sampling points within University of Ibadan campus. Netted points were set to be at least 200 m apart and checked every

thirty (30) minutes to reduce the likelihood of net destruction and escape time. The capturing was done twice daily, between 07:00–10:00 am and 4:00–7:00 pm for eight weeks between October and December, 2024. Ectoparasite samples were collected immediately after capturing, while morphometric assessment was instantaneously. Prior to samples' collection, the birds were provided with food and water *ad libitum* to ensure their general health and well-being as well as recover from capture stress.

Determination of Morphometric Parameters

The determination of the selected morphological characteristics of the sampled laughing doves was done by adapting the method of Shao *et al.* (2016). The Live Weight (LW) of each bird was determined using a sensitive weighing scale while the Head length (HL) measurement spanned from the tip of the beak to the posterior end of the skull using meter rule. The Bill length (BL) measurement was taken from the base of the upper mandible to the tip of the bill, the Tail length (TL) was measured from the base of the tail to the tip of the longest tail feather while the Wing Length (WL) measurement was taken from the shoulder joint to the tip of the longest primary feather using a meter rule. Tarsus Length (TL) measurement with a meter rule spanned from the proximal end of the tarsometatarsus to the distal end while Body Length (BL) measurement spanned from the tip of the bill to the base of the tail using a measuring tape.

Sample Collection and Laboratory Techniques

The ectoparasites in the captured birds were collected by meticulous brushing of their plumages onto a white paper, and careful extraction using thumb forceps for ectoparasites that did not fall off during the brushing (Horn *et al.*, 2017; Nahal *et al.*, 2021). Following Saranya *et al.* (2018), all the ectoparasite samples were subsequently kept in appropriately-labelled vials with 70% ethanol for preservation prior to identification. The collected ectoparasites were examined and identified under microscope following the methods of Mathison et Pritt (2014). For haemoparasites, blood samples (about 0.1 - 0.5 ml) were collected through wing venipuncture into properly labelled Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid bottles (EDTA) bottles using 1 ml insulin syringe. The blood volume range represents about 1% of each bird's weight, and which is safe to be collected from a clinically-healthy bird (Ison *et al.* 2005). Blood samples were used to prepare smears by placing single drops of blood on glass slides, spread evenly, and allowed to air dry. Absolute methanol was used to fix the thin smears, while a 10% Giemsa stain solution was used to stain the fixed smears for 15 minutes. Under a microscope with $\times 100$ object (oil immersion lens), the stained smears were viewed to detect the presence of blood parasites (Mbassi *et al.* 2022). The birds were euthanized using cervical dislocation following the euthanasia of animals' guidelines (AVMA 2020). GIT contents as well as fresh faecal samples gathered from cages of the captive birds were collected into sample bottles and preserved with 10% formalin and subjected to sedimentation and floatation techniques for parasites' detections (Latif *et al.* 2016; Ferdous *et al.* 2023). Intestinal contents were examined grossly for full or segments of adult worms (Salavati *et al.* 2023) while the eggs or oocysts were identified and counted following the McMaster counting method (Carrera-Jativa *et al.* 2018). All laboratory investigations were conducted at the research laboratory of the Veterinary Parasitology and Entomology Department in the University of Ibadan, while, parasite prevalence (Zhang *et al.* 2014) was calculated using the formula below:

$$\text{Prevalence} = \frac{\text{Total number of infected birds by a species of parasite}}{\text{Total number of birds examined}} \times 100\%$$

Statistical Analysis

The analyses involved descriptive summaries (frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation) and inferential testing using a t-test in STATA 17. To evaluate the association between infection status and sex, both Chi-square test and Firth logistic regression that is suited for small sample sizes were employed. The Firth regression estimated the odds of infection in male birds relative to females. Statistical procedures were conducted at 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) significance level.

Results

Morphometric parameters of captured laughing doves

The quantitative morphometric parameters of laughing doves show that the mean values were live weight (92.40 ± 6.52 g), tarsus length (2.61 ± 0.09 cm), bill length (1.84 ± 0.06 cm), head length (4.08 ± 0.17 cm), wing length (12.68 ± 0.67 cm), tail length (11.43 ± 0.76 cm), and body length (24.72 ± 2.10 cm). The summarized morphometric parameters are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1: Mean values of morphometric parameters of captured laughing doves

Parameters	Female	Male	Combined sex
Live weight (g)	85.50 \pm 6.61	94.13 \pm 5.41	92.40 \pm 6.52
Tarsus length (cm)	2.63 \pm 0.05	2.61 \pm 0.10	2.61 \pm 0.09
Bill length (cm)	1.80 \pm 0.00	1.84 \pm 0.06	1.84 \pm 0.06
Head length (cm)	4.03 \pm 0.05	4.09 \pm 0.19	4.08 \pm 0.17
Wing length (cm)	12.40 \pm 0.50	12.75 \pm 0.71	12.68 \pm 0.67
Tail length (cm)	11.15 \pm 0.62	11.49 \pm 0.79	11.43 \pm 0.76
Body length (cm)	22.80 \pm 3.23	25.20 \pm 1.50	24.72 \pm 2.10

Note: Results are presented as Mean \pm Standard Deviation

Sex-based Morphometric comparisons of laughing doves

The comparison of male and female morphometric parameters of captured laughing doves was analysed using t-test. The result shows that only the live weight ($t.stat. = -2.740$, $p.value = 0.013$) and body length ($t.stat. = -2.255$, $p.value = 0.037$) showed statistically significant differences between sexes. However, other parameters including tarsus length ($t.stat. = 0.359$, $p.value = 0.724$), bill length ($t.stat. = -1.363$, $p.value = 0.190$), head length ($t.stat. = -0.712$, $p.value = 0.486$), wing length ($t.stat. = -0.928$, $p.value = 0.366$), and tail length ($t.stat. = -0.805$, $p.value = 0.431$), did not show statistically significant differences as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between female and male laughing doves' morphometric parameters

Parameters	t-value	Significance	Interpretation
Live weight (g)	-2.740	0.013	Significant
Tarsus length (cm)	0.359	0.724	Not Significant
Bill length (cm)	-1.363	0.190	Not Significant
Head length (cm)	-0.712	0.486	Not Significant
Wing length (cm)	-0.928	0.366	Not Significant
Tail length (cm)	-0.805	0.431	Not Significant
Body length (cm)	-2.255	0.037	Significant

Prevalence of ectoparasites in captured laughing doves

The result of ectoparasites on the sampled bird species shows the presence of *Goniodes* sp., *Columbicola* sp., *Megninia* sp., *Ctenocephalides* sp. and *Cullicoides* sp. (Table 3). *Megninia* sp. (mites) had the highest prevalence at 60%, followed by *Goniodes* sp. (lice) at 40%. *Columbicola* sp. (lice) was observed in 15% of the samples, while *Ctenocephalides* sp. (fleas) and *Cullicoides* sp. (flies) had lower prevalence rates of 10% and 5%, respectively as shown in Figure 1. The chi-square and Firth logistic regression analyses showed no significant association between sex and infection status, with males having lower but statistically inconclusive odds of infection than females based on observed ectoparasitism.

Table 3: Ectoparasites in captured laughing doves

S/N	Sample Code	Parasites Identified [Frequency]
1	F1	<i>Columbicola</i> sp. [1]
2	F2	<i>Goniodes</i> sp. [1]
3	F3	-
4	F4	<i>Goniodes</i> sp. [2]
5	M1	<i>Cullicoides</i> sp. [5]; <i>Goniodes</i> sp. [5]; <i>Megninia</i> sp. [8]
6	M2	<i>Columbicola</i> sp. [2]
7	M3	<i>Megninia</i> sp. [2]; <i>Ctenocephalides</i> sp. [2]
8	M4	-
9	M5	<i>Goniodes</i> sp. [2]; <i>Ctenocephalides</i> sp. [1]; <i>Megninia</i> sp. [2]
10	M6	<i>Megninia</i> sp. [1]
11	M7	<i>Megninia</i> sp. [2]
12	M8	<i>Megninia</i> sp. [3]; <i>Goniodes</i> sp. [1]
13	M9	<i>Goniodes</i> sp. [2]; <i>Megninia</i> sp. [4]
14	M10	<i>Megninia</i> sp. [3]; <i>Columbicola</i> sp. [2]
15	M11	-
16	M12	<i>Goniodes</i> sp. [1]
17	M13	<i>Megninia</i> sp. [2]
18	M14	<i>Megninia</i> sp. [2]
19	M15	<i>Megninia</i> sp. [2]
20	M16	<i>Megninia</i> sp. [1]; <i>Goniodes</i> sp. [2]
<i>Statistical Tests</i>		
Chi-Square Statistic	0.3922	
Observed Odds Ratio	0.4286 (0.0695, 2.6427)	

*Note: F = Female, M = Male; the figures in square brackets denote the number of the corresponding parasites found in the sample; the cells containing a hyphen "-" indicate negative cases (where no parasites were found). The figures in parenthesis are the 95% confidence interval of the firth logistic regression estimate of the effect of sex on infection status. Parameter estimates and tests statistics with *** indicate statistical significance at 5% level, while no asterisk denote insignificance.*

Figure 1: Overall prevalence of ectoparasites on captured laughing doves

Prevalence of haemoparasites in captured laughing doves

Haemoproteus sp. and avian *Plasmodium* sp. were the only haemoparasites identified in this study (Table 4). The findings revealed *Haemoproteus* sp. as the most common haemoparasite, with a prevalence of 60% while avian *Plasmodium* sp. was detected in 30% of the samples (Figure 2). The chi-square and Firth logistic regression analyses showed males had higher but non-significant odds of infection than females.

Table 4: Haemoparasites in captured laughing doves

S/N	Sample Code	Parasites Identified
1	F1	-
2	F2	<i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
3	F3	Avian <i>Plasmodium</i> sp., <i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
4	F4	<i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
5	M1	<i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
6	M2	-
7	M3	Avian <i>Plasmodium</i> sp., <i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
8	M4	<i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
9	M5	-
10	M6	Avian <i>Plasmodium</i> sp., <i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
11	M7	<i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
12	M8	-
13	M9	-
14	M10	Avian <i>Plasmodium</i> sp.
15	M11	<i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
16	M12	-
17	M13	Avian <i>Plasmodium</i> sp., <i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
18	M14	<i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
19	M15	Avian <i>Plasmodium</i> sp., <i>Haemoproteus</i> sp.
20	M16	-
Statistical Tests		
Chi-Square Statistic	0.2198	
Observed Odds Ratio	1.4444 (0.1685, 12.3798)	

Note: F = Female, M = Male; the cells containing a hyphen “-” indicate negative cases (where no parasites were found). The figures in parenthesis are the 95% confidence interval of the firth logistic regression estimate of the effect of sex on infection status. Parameter estimates and tests statistics with *** indicate statistical significance at 5% level, while no asterisk denote insignificance.

Figure 2: Overall prevalence of haemoparasites in captured laughing doves

Prevalence of endoparasites from intestinal contents of captured laughing doves

This study observed the presence of endoparasites such as *Eimeria* oocysts, *Raillietina* sp., and *Balantidium coli* in the intestinal contents of sampled laughing doves (Table 5). The results revealed a high prevalence of *Eimeria* oocysts (90%), making it the most detected parasite. *Raillietina* sp. (Ova) was observed in 65% of the samples, while *Raillietina* sp. (adult segment) appeared in 45%, indicating active tapeworm infections in significant individuals of the sampled bird species. *Balantidium coli* was detected in 30% of the samples as shown in Figure 3. Chi-square and Firth logistic regression revealed no significant sex-based difference in infection status, though males exhibited higher but statistically non-significant odds in intestinal parasite screening.

Table 5: Endoparasites from the intestinal contents of captured laughing doves

S/N	Sample Code	Parasites Identified
1	F1	<i>Eimeria</i> sp.; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova)
2	F2	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova)
3	F3	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova); <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Adult segment)
4	F4	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova)
5	M1	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova); <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Adult segment)
6	M2	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova); <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Adult segment)
7	M3	<i>Eimeria</i> sp
8	M4	<i>Balantidium coli</i> ; <i>Eimeria</i> sp
9	M5	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova)
10	M6	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Balantidium coli</i>
11	M7	<i>Eimeria</i> sp.; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova)
12	M8	-
13	M9	<i>Balantidium coli</i> ; <i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova); <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Adult segment)
14	M10	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova); <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Adult segment); <i>Balantidium coli</i>
15	M11	<i>Balantidium coli</i> ; <i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Adult segment)
16	M12	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Balantidium coli</i> ; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Adult segment)
17	M13	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova); <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Adult segment)
18	M14	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova);
19	M15	<i>Eimeria</i> sp; <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Ova); <i>Raillietina</i> sp. (Adult segment)
20	M16	-
Statistical Tests		
Chi-Square Statistic	0.5556	
Observed Odds Ratio	1.5517 (0.0623, 38.6543)	

Note: F = Female, M = Male; the cells containing a hyphen “-” indicate negative cases (where no parasites were found). The figures in parenthesis are the 95% confidence interval of the firth logistic regression estimate of the effect of sex on infection status. Parameter estimates and tests statistics with *** indicate statistical significance at 5% level, while no asterisk denote insignificance.

Figure 3: Prevalence of endoparasites in captured laughing doves

Prevalence of parasites in fresh faecal samples of captured laughing doves

This study identified *Eimeria* sp., *Balantidium coli*, nematode larva, and *Heterakis* sp in the faeces of captured laughing doves screened (Table 6). *Eimeria* sp had the highest prevalence of 25%, followed by nematode larva (15%). *Balantidium coli* were detected in 10% of the samples, while *Heterakis* sp had the lowest prevalence at 10% (Figure 3). The Identified ectoparasites, protozoan and helminth intestinal parasites in captured laughing dove are displayed in Figure 4. Chi-square and Firth logistic regression indicated no significant sex-infection link, with males showing lower, yet statistically inconclusive, odds in faecal parasite detection.

Table 6: Parasites in fresh faecal samples of captured laughing doves

S/N	Sample Code	Parasites Identified
1	F1	-
2	F2	<i>Eimeria</i> sp
3	F3	-
4	F4	<i>Heterakis</i> sp., <i>Eimeria</i> sp
5	M1	-
6	M2	-
7	M3	<i>Eimeria</i> sp,
8	M4	-
9	M5	-
10	M6	<i>Balantidium coli</i>
11	M7	-
12	M8	<i>Balantidium coli</i>
13	M9	-
14	M10	-
15	M11	<i>Eimeria</i> sp
16	M12	-
17	M13	-
18	M14	<i>Eimeria</i> sp
19	M15	<i>Heterakis</i> sp.
20	M16	-
<i>Statistical Tests</i>		
Chi-Square Statistic	0.0505	
Observed Odds Ratio	0.7895 (0.1071, 5.8185)	

Note: F = Female, M = Male; the cells containing a hyphen "-" indicate negative cases (where no parasites were found). The figures in parenthesis are the 95% confidence interval of the firth logistic regression estimate of the effect of sex on infection status. Parameter estimates and tests statistics with *** indicate statistical significance at 5% level, while no asterisk denote insignificance.

Figure 4: Identified ectoparasites, protozoan and helminth intestinal parasites in captured laughing pigeons (A) *Columbicola* sp. (lice), (B) *Goniodes* sp (lice), (C) *Megninia* sp. (Analgidae mite), (D) *Ctenocephalides felis* (flea), female, (E) *Culicoides* sp., (F) *Balantidium coli* cysts, (G) *Raillietia* sp. egg, (H) *Eimeria* oocysts, (I) *Raillietia* sp. [adult segment], (J) *Heterakis* sp. (K) *Haemoproteus* sp. (black arrow) and Avian Plasmodium (yellow arrow)

Discussion

The morphometric analysis of the captured Laughing Doves (*Spilopelia senegalensis*) revealed significant sexual dimorphism in body length and live weight, with males consistently displaying larger sizes, most likely due to testosterone-mediated increases in muscle mass necessary for mating success. These results parallel findings by Tahir *et al.* (2022), who documented similar dimorphic patterns in the Common Hoopoe (*Upupa epops*). Comparable environmental pressures, including food availability and climatic conditions, likely contribute to the uniformity of other morphometric traits across sexes, indicating shared ecological roles (Ayadi *et al.* 2016). Such subtle yet consistent sex-based size differences align with global patterns suggesting male-biased body size dimorphism (Székely *et al.* 2007). Recent West African studies further support these observations; for instance, in urban Nigeria, birds exhibit slight male enlargement linked to ecological adaptation (Faith *et al.* 2018).

Ectoparasitological findings showed a high prevalence of mites (*Megninia* sp.) and lice (*Goniodes* sp., *Columbicola* sp.), underscoring the extensive ectoparasitic burden in wild avian populations. The predominance of *Megninia* spp. observed in the present study is consistent with previous reports from commercial laying systems in Brazil and other avian production environments across multiple continents (Sulzbach *et al.*, 2021; Horn *et al.*, 2017). These suggest the potential for transboundary dissemination through poultry trade, movement of live birds, and contact with wild avifauna that may serve as reservoirs. Although Hamza et Ndams (2024) prioritized *Goniodes* sp., our findings showed it as the second most common lice genus, echoing Tayyub *et al.* (2021), who reported similar lice species compositions in wild pigeons. Known to cause feather damage, *Megninia* sp. predisposes birds to secondary infections and thermoregulatory dysfunction (He *et al.* 2016). Louse infestation dynamics likely reflect regional environmental variability (Al-Mayah et

Hatem 2018), and their prevalence in domestic pigeons in Algeria matches observations here (Boucheikhchoukh *et al.* 2023). Conversely, *Bovicola* sp. was reported as dominant in Iraqi pigeons (Al-Badrani et Al-Muffti 2023), indicating local species differences. The presence of *Culicoides* sp. further raises concerns about vector-borne pathogen transmission, consistent with global studies on midges as disease vectors in avifauna (Mills *et al.* 2017).

Haemoparasitic infections were dominated by *Haemoproteus* sp., a trait mirrored in both our findings and prevailing avian haemoparasite surveys in West Africa (Van Hemert *et al.* 2019; Ghaemitalab *et al.* 2021). *Haemoproteus* sp. dominance in both wild African birds and local Columbidae confirms its epidemiological prominence (Wahhab *et al.* 2017). Meanwhile, the low prevalence of Avian *Plasmodium* sp. supports similar results from Nigerian *S. senegalensis* (Ali *et al.* 2024), likely linked to vector ecology and host resistance. Co-infections raise red-flag concerns about synergistic health impacts, such as anaemia and reduced fitness, highlighted in experimental avian malaria models globally (Schoenle *et al.* 2017).

The dominance of *Eimeria* oocysts in faecal samples underscores heightened coccidiosis risk, particularly in ground-foraging species. Similar prevalence rates have been reported in Nigerian poultry (Lawal *et al.*, 2016) and European wild birds (Crespo-Ginés *et al.* 2019; Berto et Lopes 2020). Communal feeding and roosting are critical risk factors for transmission (Carrera-Játiva *et al.* 2018). Detection of *Raillietina* sp. tapeworms, requiring insect intermediate hosts, points to regular ingestion of infected arthropods. Such prevalence aligns with Iraqi avian studies (Huda et Ali 2022) and reinforces the doves' ecological role in helminth cycles. Adult cestode identification suggests chronic infection establishment.

Additional gastrointestinal findings, nematodes and *Balantidium coli*, suggest broader enteric risk, as seen in Nigerian avian surveys (Byun *et al.* 2021). The low occurrence of *Heterakis* sp. likely stems from dietary preferences that limit exposure to soil-dwelling intermediate hosts, aligning with studies among granivorous birds in West Africa (Bairwa 2024). The overall parasitic spectrum illustrates the multi-faceted health challenges faced by wild bird populations, with implications for monitoring avian-wildlife interfaces and zoonotic risk assessment. High parasite prevalence in wild doves underscores potential spillover risks to domestic birds, livestock, and humans, especially in urban-wildlife interfaces where shared habitat usage occurs (Franklin *et al.* 2021). Understanding size dimorphism and parasite burdens informs conservation strategies by showcasing the ecological pressure exerted by parasitism on bird fitness, breeding success, and survival. These findings support expansion of avian parasitology monitoring in Nigeria and West Africa, contributing essential data for veterinary health databases and informing bird disease interventions. Consistency with international studies demonstrates that *Columbidae* species across regions share similar parasitic and morphometric profiles, advocating for collaborative surveillance and control measures.

Conclusion

The findings of this study contribute to a broader understanding of avian morphometry as well as parasite ecology in captured *Spilopelia senegalensis* within the University of Ibadan campus. Specifically, the study noted statistically significant sex differentials of the live weight and body length of examined laughing doves attributable to sexual dimorphism. Also, *Megninia* sp. and *Haemoproteus* sp. were observed to be the most prevalent ectoparasite and haemoparasite, respectively while *Eimeria* sp. was noted as the most predominant Gastrointestinal Tract (GIT) and faecal

parasite. In all, the study indicated that sampled *Spilopelia senegalensis* experienced a substantial parasitic burden which may affect their survival and are of ecological health concern. No significant sex-based difference in infection status were observed for the different samples. There is need for further studies which will incorporate molecular diagnostics for specific parasite identification.

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Conflict of Interest

There are no conflict of interests among authors.

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